

ASSOCIATION OF INFLAMMATORY BIOMARKERS AND INSULIN RESISTANCE WITH ISCHEMIC STROKE SUBTYPES

Qutlibika Abdurakhmonova PhD

DSc researcher of Tashkent State Medical University

+998973579900

Doctor.abdurakhmonova@gmail.com

Annotation. *This thesis investigates the relationship between ischemic stroke subtypes and circulating inflammatory biomarkers, with a special emphasis on the role of insulin resistance (IR) as a metabolic factor. Results of the study highlights the importance of integrating metabolic and inflammatory markers to improve stroke classification, prognosis, and targeted management.*

Key words. *ischemic stroke; inflammatory biomarkers; insulin resistance; ICAM-1; hs-CRP; systemic immune-inflammation index (SII); neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR); TOAST classification; prognosis; pathophysiology*

Background. Advances in biomarker research provide new opportunities to clarify the pathophysiological mechanisms of ischemic stroke. This study aimed to examine the relationship between ischemic stroke subtypes and circulating inflammatory biomarkers, with a particular focus on the contribution of insulin resistance (IR) as a metabolic factor.

Methods. A total of 68 patients with acute ischemic stroke were analyzed and compared with 32 healthy controls. Stroke etiology was classified according to the TOAST (Trial of Org 10172 in Acute Stroke Treatment) system. Serum concentrations of intercellular adhesion molecule-1 (ICAM-1), high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP), systemic immune-inflammation index (SII), and neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) were measured. In addition, fasting glucose and insulin were obtained to calculate HOMA-IR for assessment of insulin resistance.

Results. Cardioembolic strokes demonstrated the highest inflammatory activity, with mean ICAM-1, hs-CRP, SII, and NLR values of 328.47 ± 196.83 , 4.75 ± 2.26 , 2006.33 ± 1769.41 , and 9.03 ± 8.27 , respectively. By contrast, lacunar strokes showed the lowest levels (151.64 ± 47.94 , 2.3 ± 1.17 , 554.6 ± 470.6 , and 3.03 ± 2.58). Large artery atherosclerosis and cryptogenic strokes presented intermediate biomarker values. Insulin resistance was detected in 41.2% of patients and was consistently associated with higher ICAM-1, hs-CRP, and NLR levels across all subtypes, as well as poorer short-term functional outcomes.

Conclusions. Both inflammatory biomarkers and insulin resistance differ significantly across ischemic stroke subtypes and contribute to disease heterogeneity. The coexistence of IR and elevated inflammatory activity may help explain worse clinical outcomes in certain patients. These findings highlight the potential of combining metabolic and inflammatory markers to improve etiological classification, prognosis, and targeted management in ischemic stroke.

References

1. Tuttolomondo A, Simonetta I, Daidone M, Mogavero A, Ortello A, Pinto A. Metabolic and vascular risk factors in ischemic stroke: role of inflammatory and immune mechanisms. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2019;20(23):6248.
2. Pan Y, Jing J, Zhao X, Zheng H, Jia Q, Mi D, et al. Insulin resistance and outcomes of nondiabetic patients with ischemic stroke: the ACROSS-China study. *Stroke.* 2016;47(2):470–6.
3. Ji R, Meng X, Fang H, Han M, Yang Q, Ding Y, et al. High neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio is associated with poor outcomes in acute ischemic stroke after intravenous thrombolysis. *Front Neurol.* 2019;10:131.
4. Zhong C, Xu T, Xu T, Peng Y, Wang A, Wang J, et al. Plasma homocysteine and prognosis of acute ischemic stroke: a prospective cohort study. *Stroke.* 2017;48(3):561–6.
5. Guo D, Zhu Z, Zhong C, Peng H, Xu T, Chen C, et al. Prognostic value of neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio in acute ischemic stroke patients. *Front Neurol.* 2019;10:1206.
6. Kernan WN, Ovbiagele B, Black HR, Bravata DM, Chimowitz MI, Ezekowitz MD, et al. Guidelines for the prevention of stroke in patients with stroke and transient ischemic attack. *Stroke.* 2014;45(7):2160–236.
7. Jin R, Yang G, Li G. Inflammatory mechanisms in ischemic stroke: role of inflammatory cells. *J Leukoc Biol.* 2010;87(5):779–89.
8. Li J, Zhao X, Meng X, Pan Y, Liu L, Wang Y, et al. High-sensitivity C-reactive protein predicts recurrent stroke and poor functional outcome: subgroup analysis of the CHANCE trial. *Stroke.* 2016;47(8):2025–30.
9. Bae HJ, Yoon DS, Lee J, Kim BK, Koo JS, Kim HS, et al. Inflammatory markers and the risk of early recurrent stroke. *Stroke.* 2012;43(11):2914–21.
10. Wang A, Liu J, Meng X, Wang Y. Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio and clinical outcomes in ischemic stroke patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front Neurol.* 2022;13:819495.

11. Shoamanesh A, Preis SR, Beiser AS, Vasan RS, Benjamin EJ, Kase CS, et al. Inflammatory biomarkers, cerebral microbleeds, and small vessel disease: Framingham Heart Study. *Neurology*. 2015;84(8):825–32.
12. Zhang J, Ren Q, Song Y, He M, Zeng Y, Liu Z. Association of systemic immune-inflammation index with functional outcomes in acute ischemic stroke. *Neurol Sci*. 2020;41(10):2885–92.